

Impact of Explanations on Transparency, User Satisfaction and Persuasiveness in Personalized Product Recommendations

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Abstract

The absence of explanations in recommender systems and the opaque nature of these systems have been challenging despite their role in personalizing financial product offerings, resulting in limited user satisfaction and trust. This study explores the impact of explanations on user perceptions of transparency, satisfaction and persuasiveness in Personalized Product Recommender (PPR) systems within the financial services domain. One hundred and seventy unique participants were recruited. The interaction yielded 135 evaluation responses for the PPR system and 148 for the PPRE system. Participants completed a structured survey measuring their perceptions across the constructs. The researchers used descriptive statistics and Mann-Whitney U tests to evaluate and compare the systems. Results revealed statistically significant differences, with the PPRE system achieving higher median scores across all constructs: transparency ($U = 1491.000$, $p < .001$), user satisfaction ($U = 962.000$, $p < .001$), and persuasiveness ($U = 1426.500$, $p < .001$). These findings demonstrate that integrating transparent and user-centred explanations improves user experience and trust in financial recommender systems.

Keywords: Personalized Product Recommender systems, Explainable AI, Transparent explanations, User satisfaction, Perceived Transparency, Persuasiveness, Human-Centered AI, Evaluation, Information Systems.

Introduction

Recommender systems have been developed and applied in various domains, including Human-Computer Interaction, Artificial Intelligence, Information Retrieval, and Expert Systems, and it is possible based on multidisciplinary approaches [1], [2]. The financial sector is a significant domain where such approaches

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are highly relevant, where institutions face intense competition and must differentiate their services. Banks offer different products and services, including savings and current accounts, loans, investments, money transfer services, personal and business travel allowances, credit and debit cards, insurance, and digital banking solutions.

Despite the advances in recommender systems, users often find it challenging to understand why specific products are recommended to them. This lack of transparency in generating recommendations can reduce customers' trust and make them hesitant about adopting the recommended products. Explanations not only build transparency but also improve user satisfaction and persuasiveness, making them essential components of recommender systems. Addressing these challenges necessitates the development of recommender systems that offer personalized product offerings and clear and persuasive explanations that improve transparency and user satisfaction.

Personalized Product Recommender (PPR) systems are a collection of software tools and methodologies that provide individualized products to users based on their unique attributes- preferences, interests, behaviours, and other features. Users will be able to discover more products using the PPR systems. They can be applied in domains such as e-commerce, finance, and entertainment, where there are various products or items, but the users are just interested in a fraction [7].

Recent studies have shown the need for incorporating explanations in recommender systems to eliminate opacity resulting from their "black-box" nature. Explanations also improve transparency, trust and user satisfaction [3], [4],[8]. In [5], Zhang and Chen highlighted that explainable recommendations help users understand the rationale behind such suggestions, thereby improving the effectiveness of the systems. They also align with several key attributes that enhance the quality of user experience such as scrutability, validity, trust, effectiveness, efficiency, transparency, user satisfaction, and persuasiveness. Scrutability allows users to check and correct assumptions made by the system, ensuring control over decisions. Validity provides users with adequate information to make well-informed decisions. Trust is established when explanations clarify the rationale behind a recommendation, reinforcing user confidence. Effectiveness measures how well the explanations help users make decisions that align with their preferences. Efficiency ensures that explanations provided help users make quick and accurate decisions with minimal effort. Transparency involves showing the reasons behind recommendations, and helping users assess their relevance. User satisfaction measures how well recommender systems with explanations meet users' expectations and needs. Persuasiveness is the ability of explanations to influence users' purchasing decisions by persuading them to proceed with the recommended product or discouraging them if the justification does not align with their expectations and needs [6].

In addition to justifying recommendations, explanations provide detailed product descriptions that help customers understand the product features for more informed decision-making. This approach supports the broader objectives and attributes of explanations in recommender systems, which include transparency, trust, persuasiveness, effectiveness and user satisfaction [5].

This study investigates the impact of explanations in the Personalized Product Recommender (PPR) system, examining how explanations impact transparency, user satisfaction, and persuasiveness in banking recommendations.

Research question

The study focuses on two (2) key research questions:

1. How do explanations in personalized product recommender (PPR) systems influence users' perception of transparency, user satisfaction, and persuasiveness in banking recommendations?
2. Is there a significant difference in perceived transparency, user satisfaction, and persuasiveness between personalized product recommender systems with and without explanations?

Research Method

This study builds upon earlier work focused solely on transparency by expanding the evaluation to include two additional constructs: user satisfaction and persuasiveness. The survey instrument was embedded within the developed recommender system and deployed on the *skillsdemy.com* domain hosted by OwnRegistrar Inc.

Participant recruitment was conducted through invitation, with no financial incentives provided. One hundred and seventy invitations were sent, resulting in 148 valid responses for the Personalized Recommender (PPR) system with explanations and 135 responses for the PPR system without explanations. Respondents were 18 to 70 years old and from a broad range of professional backgrounds, including 22% students, 13% financial sector employees, 23% traders/entrepreneurs, 18% civil servants, and 24% from other professions.

Each participant received a link to the recommender system and instructions on onboarding and navigating the platform. The application displayed a data privacy policy to ensure transparency in data handling. Participants manually entered basic demographic information, while the system also captured data such as geographic location.

The system analysed each participant's profile to generate tailored financial product recommendations. Following system interaction, participants completed a structured survey using a 5-point Likert scale to assess their experiences based on perceived transparency, user satisfaction, and persuasiveness (Table 1). This procedure was replicated across both system versions, enabling comparative analysis of the constructs.

Table 1. Survey items and Item measurement for evaluating the recommender system from a user perspective.

Item Number	Construct	Survey Item	Item measurement Focus
1	Perceived Transparency	The system clearly explains why this product was recommended to me.	Understanding the rationale behind recommendations
2	Perceived Transparency	The recommendation and explanation provided detailed information about the product's pricing, features and benefits.	Clarity and sufficiency of product information.
3	Perceived Transparency	The recommended product aligns with my needs, preferences, and lifestyle.	Perceived relevance of recommendation
4	Perceived Transparency	The clarity of explanation increases my willingness to consider the product.	Impact of perceived transparency on purchase decision.
5	User satisfaction	I like the product more after reading the recommendation/explanation.	Change in product perception.
6	User satisfaction	I am satisfied with the recommended product and explanation.	Satisfaction with both recommendation and explanation.
7	User satisfaction	I would likely buy this product based on appealing the recommendations and explanations.	Impact of user satisfaction with the recommendation and explanation on purchase intention.
8	Persuasiveness	Understanding why the product was recommended increases my likelihood of requesting it.	Influence of explanation on intent to act.

9	Persuasiveness.	My perception of the product changed after understanding the explanation.	Persuasive impact of explanations on product perceptions.
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Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis outcome comparing the Personalized Product Recommender (PPR) and Personalized Product Recommender with Explanations (PPRE) across three constructs: Perceived transparency, User Satisfaction and Persuasiveness.

Descriptive statistics

Table 2 summarizes the descriptive statistics of each construct. Users of the PPRE system consistently reported higher perceptions of transparency, greater satisfaction with the recommended products, and a higher likelihood of persuasion by the recommendations than the users of the PPR system.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for PPR and PPRE systems.

Construct	PPR (n = 135)	PPRE(n=148)
Transparency	2.81 ± 0.63	4.31 ± 0.69
User satisfaction	2.70 ± 0.71	4.31 ± 0.69
Persuasiveness	3.02 ± 0.73	4.51 ± 0.67

The results show a remarkable increase across the three constructs of the PPRE system, providing preliminary evidence that explanations in product recommendations enhance user experience. In addition to the tabular summary, Figure 1 presents a bar chart comparing the distribution of scores across both systems. The plot highlights those participants who used the PPRE system consistently reported higher scores and less variability across all constructs than those who used the PPR system.

Figure 1. Bar chart comparing transparency, user satisfaction, and persuasiveness scores between the Personalized Product Recommender (PPR) and the PPR with Explanations (PPRE) systems measured using a 5-point Likert scale.

Inferential Statistics: Mann-Whitney U Test

We conducted the Mann-Whitney U test to assess whether the observed differences between the systems' three constructs were significant. This non-parametric test was chosen due to the ordinal nature of the Likert-scale responses and non-normal distribution. The results of the Mann-Whitney U test revealed statistically significant differences across all three constructs:

- i. **Transparency:** Participants who accessed the PPRE system reported significantly higher transparency scores than those who accessed the PPR system ($U = 1491$, $Z = -12.415$, $p < .001$).
- ii. **User Satisfaction:** Satisfaction scores were also significantly greater for PPRE system users compared to PPR system users ($U = 962$, $Z = -13.257$, $p < .001$).
- iii. **Persuasiveness:** Similarly, persuasiveness ratings were significantly greater for PPRE system users than for PPR system users ($U = 1426.5$, $Z = -12.641$, $p < .001$).

The results confirm that including explanations in the recommender system positively influences users' perceptions of transparency, increases their satisfaction with the system and enhances the persuasive effect of the recommendations. These results support the study's hypotheses, indicating that users of the PPRE system reported significantly higher perceived transparency, user satisfaction, and persuasiveness than the users of the PPR system.

Conclusion

The study investigated the impact of explanations on perceived transparency, user satisfaction and persuasiveness in personalized product recommendations for financial services. The study compared user responses between a Personalized Product Recommender (PPR) system and an enhanced version with transparent explanations (PPRE) and found that users who received recommendations accompanied by explanations reported higher scores across all three constructs.

The findings affirm the impact of integrating human-centred explanations in recommender systems, particularly in the financial domain, where decision-making involves higher stakes and greater cognitive demands. Clear and relevant explanations help customers understand the rationale behind recommendations and contribute meaningfully to their overall satisfaction with the system and their likelihood to act on the recommendations.

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